

Negative Staining Procedure

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----- **Principles & Scope of Application** -----

The procedure is used to prepare suspensions for the analysis of small and thin particles (usually thinner than 1 µm) by transmission electron microscopy. Possible applications: Search and determination of viruses and other small microorganisms in medical samples; quality assessment of virus or nanoparticle suspensions; analysis of large macromolecular aggregates or polymers.

Principle of the method: Particles of the sample suspension are adsorbed at the surface of the sample support and embedded in a thin film of amorphous heavy metal salts. This procedure stabilizes the particles and allows visualization of structural details.

The procedure comprises several steps: (1) Grids with carbon enhanced plastic films are coated with Alcian Blue, which produces a positively charged surface. (2) The sample suspension is added to the grid (drop-on-grid) for particle adsorption. (3) The adsorbed particles are washed and (4) incubated with a solution of heavy metal salts (uranyl acetate or phosphotungstic acid). (5) Grids are blotted and dried.

----- **Lab Safety** -----

Safety rules differ locally. Please follow your local rules and/or consult your safety officer.

Chemicals can be harmful. Consider safety information, wear suitable personal protection (lab coat, gloves and goggles) and handle the waste according to local rules.

Samples may be harmful (e.g. infectious) or posing a risk to the environment. It is necessary to assess the risks of working with them. In most cases an official permission to work with such samples is necessary. Some general considerations regarding biosafety are summarized in the section "Remarks".

----- **Materials** -----

- (1) Sample suspension
- (2) Forceps for handling the grids (inverted forceps are needed for the adsorption; see also "Remarks")
- (3) Alcian Blue 8 GX, C.I. 74240, EC No. 2783338; Fluka (Sigma-Aldrich, Nr. 05500-5G)
- (4) Acetic acid, 100%
- (5) Uranyl acetate, 1% in de-ionized water, pH 4,5
- (6) Phosphotungstic acid, 1% in de-ionized water, pH 7
- (7) Grids, 400 mesh, copper, filmed with formvar or pioloform plastic and enhanced with

a layer of carbon (~10 nm)

- (8) De-ionized water
- (9) Filter paper
- (10) Microliter pipette (10-100 μ l) with single-use tips
- (11) Parafilm
- (12) Grid storage container
- (13) Cover for shielding the droplets with the grids during incubation
- (14) Desktop centrifuge
- (15) Vortex mixer
- (16) Magnetic stirrer
- (17) Ultrasonic bath (optional)

----- **Preparation of Alcian Blue** -----

Stock Solution I:

- (18) Dissolve 2% (w/v) Alcian Blue in double distilled water. Put solution in an ultrasonic bath for 10 min to increase speed of solution.
- (19) Centrifuge solution for 1h at 10.000 – 14.000 g at room temperature.
- (20) Collect supernatant carefully and store it at 4° C.

Stock solution II:

- (21) Mix acetic acid (2% v/v) with distilled water by slowly adding acid to the water while stirring the whole mixture on a magnetic stirrer (the mixture is getting extremely warm during mixing).

Solution for Application:

- (22) Mix Stock solution I with stock solution II in equal amounts. The final concentration of Alcian Blue is 1%.

All solutions can be stored for at least 6 months in the refrigerator (4-8° C).

----- **Application** -----

- (23) Centrifuge all solutions, except of the sample suspension, in a desktop centrifuge at highest speed for 10 min.
- (24) Vortex the sample suspension rigorously (three times for 10 sec each).
- (25) Fix a strip of parafilm on the desk.
- (26) Place two drops (30 μ l) Alcian Blue (1%) per sample suspension on the parafilm.

- (27) Put grids on the Alcian Blue droplets and incubate them for 1 min.
- (28) Wash the grids by placing them briefly (1-2 sec.) on four droplets (30 μ l) of de-ionized water. After the last washing step blot the grid using a filter paper and proceed immediately to the next step (do not dry the grid surface completely).
- (29) Sample adsorption: Vortex the sample suspension briefly. Take the grids with an inverted forceps, the coated side facing up, and add 10 μ l of sample suspension (drop-on-grid). Incubate for 10 min. Shield the grids from dust by using a cover.
- (30) Shortly before end of incubation: For each sample suspension, place two rows with three droplets (30 μ l) of water on the parafilm. Add one droplet (30 μ l) of uranyl acetate and one droplet (30 μ l) of phosphotungstic acid.
- (31) Wash the grids by placing them briefly (1-2 sec.) on three droplets (30 μ l) of de-ionized water. After the last washing step blot the grid with a filter paper and proceed immediately to the next step (do not dry it completely).
- (32) Add a drop (30 μ l) of uranyl acetate and a drop (30 μ l) of phosphotungstic acid to the parafilm and place the grids briefly (1-2 sec) either on the uranyl acetate or the phosphotungstic acid with the treated side facing down
- (33) Blot the grids dry with a filter paper (see "Remarks")
- (34) Store the grids in grid box container

See Fig. 1 for a schematic representation of the procedure and Figs. 2-8 for some staining examples.

A video is available on the web (www.zenodo.org), which demonstrates the entire procedure -> doi 10.5281/zenodo.1468500

----- **Remarks** -----

This **standard procedure** has been published in a book chapter along with a description of our standard protocol for ultrathin section electron microscopy (Laue 2010). A few parameters of this procedure (e.g. incubation time) were investigated in a paper by Laue & Bannert (2010).

The **adsorption procedure** drop-on-grid usually produces the highest particle number on the grid surface even with small particles. Longer incubation times (e.g. 30 min) increase the particle number adsorbed. If inverted forceps are not available or not preferred, the grid can be laterally inserted into a droplet (30 μ l) of the sample suspension for particle adsorption. However, sample suspensions which contain a high number of large particles or aggregates besides smaller particles of interest, may cause an overload of the grid using drop-on-grid adsorption. In such cases placing the grid on a drop of sample suspension for particle adsorption (grid-on-drop) may help to reduce adsorption of larger and denser particles in relation to smaller particles (see the video).

The standard **concentration of the staining solutions** is 1%. If dense or large particles in the sample are of interest (e.g. bacteria), reduction of the concentration to 0.5-0.2% may improve the visibility of structural details (Figure 5, 6).

For the generation of an appropriate **heavy metal contrast film**, the grid finally is blotted

with a filter paper. Blotting the grid dry after phosphotungstic acid incubation usually results in sufficient staining quality (i.e. blotting is not critical). Uranyl acetate contrasting needs careful blotting otherwise the contrast film develops not sufficiently resulting in a “dry staining” which masks structural details. To produce an appropriate contrast film, touch the filter paper with the grid edge at an angle of about 45 ° and remove the grid before the fluid is completely absorbed by the filter paper. This procedure produces a contrast film with a gradual thickness on the grid which helps to find the perfect contrast for the particles of interest.

Forceps should be cleaned directly after use by incubation in liquids. We use incubation in 5% Lysoform disinfection solution, which contains formaldehyde, for at least 10 min. After incubation we rinse the forceps with de-ionized water and finally clean them with a paper towel soaked with 70% ethanol.

Biosafety rules are locally different. In any case, the operator should make a risk assessment for all procedures and should check if all legal aspects are met (e.g. whether an official permission is necessary to handle the sample or not). **Inactivation** of sample suspensions can be done by incubation with 2% paraformaldehyde in buffer (final concentration) for 30 min at 25 °C followed by 30 min at 37 °C on a shaker. This procedure inactivates even comparatively high concentrations of test viruses efficiently (Möller et al. 2015).

Pre-treatment of **clinical samples**, such as stool, swabs, blisters, tissue biopsies is described by Miller (1986).

References:

Laue, M. (2010): Electron microscopy of viruses. *Methods Cell Biology* 96: 1.

Laue, M., Bannert, N. (2011) Detection limit of negative staining electron microscopy for the diagnosis of bioterrorism-related microorganisms. *Journal of Applied Microbiology* 109: 1159.

Miller, S.E. (1986): Detection and identification of viruses by electron microscopy. *Journal of Electron Microscopy Technique* 4: 265-301.

Möller, L.; Schünadel, L.; Nitsche, A.; Schwebke, I.; Hanisch, M.; Laue, M. (2015): Evaluation of virus inactivation by formaldehyde to enhance biosafety of diagnostic electron microscopy. *Viruses* 7: 666.

----- Images -----

Figure 1 Schematic workflow of the entire procedure

Figure 2 Cowpox virus, cell culture supernatant (1% uranyl acetate)

Figure 3 Stool sample of a patient from a gastroenteritis outbreak (0.5 % phosphotungstic acid)

Figure 4 Norovirus aggregate from the stool sample of Fig. 3 (bar = 100 nm)

Figure 5 Bacterial cells of *Acinetobacter equii* (0.5 % uranyl acetate)

Figure 6 Detail of Figure 5 showing the pilus structures associated with the bacterial cells

Figure 7 PLGA nanoparticles loaded with magnetite particles (0.5% phosphotungstic acid)

Figure 8 Same sample and grid as in Fig. 7 but a region where the contrast film did not form properly (“dry staining”) which caused a collapse of the PLGA nanoparticles. Only the magnetite aggregates are visible.

----- **Disclaimer** -----

The author made every effort to provide timely and accurate information. Nevertheless, mistakes may occur. The authors do not assume liability for relevance, accuracy and completeness of the information provided.

Please send comments on the protocol or on experiences of applications directly to the author.